

**A QUALITATIVE EXPLORATION OF EDUCATIONAL LEADERSHIP APPROACHES:
NAVIGATING CHALLENGES FACED BY PHILIPPINE SCHOOL PRINCIPALS IN THE
TURBULENT TIMES OF COVID-19 - A CORRESPONDENCE ARTICLE**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10499735>

ABSTRACT

This qualitative study builds on Cahapay's (2021) ideas to examine how Filipino school principals in grades K -12 dealt with the COVID-19 problem. The study uses a literature review method to bring together what is already known about how educational leaders led during the pandemic. Findings show six main themes that show how principals have changed how they lead: navigating with adaptive leadership, developing crisis management skills, dealing with reliance on technology, freezing traditional standards, encouraging inclusivity in remote learning, and putting essential needs first. These changes show how strong and creative school directors are when things go wrong, and they point the way toward more caring ways of leading. The study stresses how important it is for school leadership programs to adapt to modern needs by focusing on skills like adaptable leadership, handling crises, and integrating technology.

Overall, this study adds to our knowledge of being a good leader in an educational setting during a crisis. It also gives us a starting point for policy suggestions and future research.

Keywords: *Qualitative Study, Educational Leadership, COVID-19 Crisis, School Principals, Adaptive Leadership*

INTRODUCTION

Educational leaders worldwide have encountered unprecedented circumstances due to the COVID-19 pandemic, including the Philippines. Cahapay (2021) presents a study that offers significant insights into these principals' leadership practices and experiences amidst the current difficult circumstances. Particularly from those at the vanguard of the educational system—school principals—rapid and adaptable reactions have been necessary due to the pandemic's dynamic and perpetually changing characteristics (Saagyum & Saleem, 2022). These leaders have encountered challenges and obstacles while responding to the effects of the pandemic on school operations, showcasing resilience and creative thinking. This qualitative research investigates the domain of educational leadership, aiming to examine and comprehend the varied strategies implemented by school principals in the Philippines when confronted with the complex obstacles presented by the disruptive period of COVID-19.

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly transformed the educational landscape, requiring leaders to navigate an unprecedented period of uncertainty while innovating and formulating strategies (Reyes-Guerra, Maslin-Ostrowski, Barakat, & Stefanovic, 2021). Particularly, school principals have been confronted with the challenge of balancing their institutions' ongoing requirements with the pandemic's initial effects.

The primary objective of this research is to expand upon the findings of Cahapay (2021) through an in-depth examination of the principals' actual experiences, leadership approaches, and the obstacles they encountered throughout the pandemic. The results of this investigation will likely build upon the existing literature on educational leadership during times of crisis and serve as a foundation for policy suggestions and further scholarly inquiry.

Research Questions

This study explores the lived experiences of these principals, their leadership styles, and the challenges they have faced during the pandemic.

Research question: How have Philippine school principals adapted their leadership practices to navigate the educational landscape during the virulent times of COVID-19?

METHODOLOGY

This correspondence article examines the challenges encountered by school principals throughout the pandemic, their leadership styles, and their personal experiences. The subject matter was selected due to its ability to facilitate an in-depth and intricate examination of educational

leaders' experiences and leadership methodologies. Data was obtained through an extensive literature review instead of conducting interviews to acquire primary data. Citing the authors and publications, the researcher conducted a thorough search for articles, reports, and other pertinent literature on the subject. The process comprised understanding the data, performing a theme search, evaluating the identified themes, assigning definitions and names, and ultimately generating a report.

DISCUSSION

In the context of exploring educational leadership approaches, this correspondence aims to present the lived experiences of these principals, their leadership styles, and the challenges they have faced during the pandemic.

For the research question: How have Philippine school principals adapted their leadership practices to navigate the educational landscape during the virulent times of COVID-19?

Based on the study by Cahapay (2021), Philippine school principals have adapted their leadership practices during the COVID-19 pandemic in several ways:

1. Navigating the crisis with adaptive leadership: They have demonstrated flexibility and adaptability in their leadership approach to respond effectively to rapidly changing circumstances.
2. Cultivating practices in crisis management: They have developed and implemented strategies to manage the various crises due to the pandemic.
3. Managing through the machine: They have organized the increased reliance on technology for remote learning, ensuring that teachers are trained to use online platforms, students have access to necessary devices and internet connectivity, and that online classes are conducted smoothly.
4. Freezing the standards and patterns: They have paused or modified traditional educational practices and standards in response to the pandemic.
5. Promoting inclusivity in the new normal: They have ensured that all students, including those with limited access to technology or other resources, can participate in remote learning.
6. Caring first for what is essential: They have prioritized the most critical needs of the school community during the crisis.

These adaptations highlight the resilience and innovation of school principals in the face of adversity. The study suggests that these practices are becoming more humanitarian than ever, breaking away from the customs of the old times. It also emphasizes the need for educational leadership preparation programs to be relevant to the current situation, focusing on developing essential skills related to adaptive leadership, crisis management, and technology integration.

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, this research highlights the uncharted territory of the experiences of principals of K–12 schools in the Philippines during the current worldwide emergency, specifically about the COVID-19 pandemic. Examining six emerging themes in educational leadership practices amidst this crisis offers a comprehensive insight into the strategies leaders employ to navigate and influence the educational environment amidst unprecedented circumstances. These themes include adaptive leadership, crisis management, technology integration, adherence to standards, promotion of inclusivity, and prioritization of essentials.

According to the study's findings, educational leadership has undergone a substantial transformation from the 'old normal' to the current crisis. Instead of regarding this change in a negative light, it highlights the ever-evolving character of educational leadership in action. An important implication of this is that educational leadership preparation programs must be reevaluated immediately to meet the requirements of the current environment. It is imperative to prioritize cultivating critical competencies, including but not limited to adaptive leadership, crisis management, and technology integration.

Furthermore, the research findings demonstrate a significant transformation in leadership methodologies as they increasingly adopt a humanitarian perspective. It is recommended that leaders engage in introspection regarding these dynamic practices, modify their principles accordingly, promote inclusive education, and place human needs first. The trends that have been observed indicate a deviation from traditional practices, underscoring the need for educators and practitioners to adapt to the evolving educational environment and its demands.

Fundamentally, the study enhances comprehension regarding educational leadership practices in times of crisis and provides practitioners, educators, and scholars with practical insights. Given the unprecedented consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic, the significance of transforming leadership underscores the necessity for ongoing introspection, flexibility, and a more empathetic methodology when determining the trajectory of educational leadership.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This paper has a single author and confirms that the author reviewed this study.

Funding

This work received no specific grant from any funding agency.

Acknowledgments

I extend my heartfelt gratitude to Almighty God for the strength and guidance. Special thanks to family and friends; your love and understanding fueled my perseverance. To the researchers whose work has been referenced in this paper. Their valuable insights and findings have substantially contributed to the analysis of this study.

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